

Psychological Well-being in Youth: The Role of Hope and Resilience: A Review

Parveen Kumar, Parul Patneja, and Sandeep Singh

Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar, Haryana

Youth face various challenges, including social, academic, job-related, and environmental challenges that influence their psychological well-being. Hope and resilience have become important psychological resources that can promote the psychological well-being of the youth. The present review paper aims to understand the role of hope and resilience on the psychological well-being of youth through the integration of existing studies. For youth, psychological well-being is expressed in emotional stability, self-confidence, positive social relationships, and a sense of meaning in life. Research indicates that psychological well-being in youth has strong effects on mental health and social competence. Hope plays an important role in goal setting, academic motivation, and coping with challenges. Young people who have hope are more likely to believe that problems are solvable and keep going, even when things go wrong. Hope is theoretically associated with cognitive evaluation processes that affect emotional regulation and adaptive behavior, therefore enhancing psychological well-being. Studies show that young people who are more hopeful and resilient are happier with their lives, have more supportive relationships, and have more subjective well-being. Some research also shows that resilience may act as a mediator in the relationship between hope and psychological well-being, indicating their interconnectedness. Overall, the review shows that hope and resilience are psychological resources that facilitate the psychological well-being of youth.

Keywords: Resilience, hope, psychological well-being, youth

Youth is generally defined as individuals aged 15-29 years, marked by many changes in biological, psychological, and social roles (Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, 2022). The changes in hormones impact the physical growth of youth; similarly, psychological factors such as autonomy, identity formation, and social support influence their overall well-being. These changes can help young people grow and learn more about themselves, but they can also make them more stressed, unsure, and psychologically weak (Arnett, 2000). It is an important and sensitive phase of life. This stage of life is important for personal growth as well as the growth of the world. They are an energetic and enthusiastic part of society. Youth face major life changes such as increased academic pressures, career planning, identity formation, enhanced autonomy, and changes in social demands. Academic

competitiveness, unemployment worries, peer pressure, family expectations, social media influence, and socio-economic problems have all made mental health problems worse for young people in today's society.

Psychological well-being among youth includes emotional balance, self-acceptance, purposeful living, positive interpersonal relationships, personal growth, and the ability to manage life challenges effectively (Ryff, 1989). It is suggested that a high level of psychological well-being in youth is related to higher academic achievement, healthier relationships, greater life satisfaction, and a lower risk of mental health issues in adulthood (Ryff & Keyes, 1995). According to Yiğit and Çakmak (2024), psychological well-being encompasses emotional and mental health, including self-acceptance, life satisfaction, stress management, and a sense of purpose. Hope and resilience, among other positive psychological resources, have received increased attention due to their importance in youth mental health and well-being (Snyder, 2002). Research suggests that youth who possess higher levels of both hope and resilience are better equipped to manage stress, maintain emotional stability, and experience greater satisfaction and meaning in life (Lasota & Mróz, 2021; Murphy, 2023; Yildirim & Arslan, 2020). A feeling of purpose in life enhances resilience, enabling individuals to face adversity with more determination (Frankl, 2020; Steger et al., 2021). This sense of purpose offers guidance that promotes emotional stability and well-being (Lee & Chen, 2020). Laranjeira and Querido (2022) proposed that hope and optimism help individuals cope better with stressors and are associated with higher life satisfaction, emotional well-being, and resilience. Werner (2011) found that subjective well-being is positively predicted by hope, whereas unmet needs reduce subjective well-being among individuals with serious mental illness. The study shows the importance of hope and the fulfillment of needs for recovery and overall well-being.

Author Note

Parveen Kumar, Research Scholar, Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar, Haryana

E-mail: parveengodara102@gmail.com

Parul Patneja, Research Scholar, Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar Haryana

Sandeep Singh, Professor, Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar Haryana

E-mail: sandeephisar@gmail.com

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Parul Patneja, Research Scholar, Department of Applied Psychology, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar Haryana

E-mail: parulpatneja@gmail.com

Psychological Well-being

Psychological well-being is a multidimensional concept that goes beyond the mere absence of mental illness, including optimal psychological experience. Ryff's model of psychological well-being defines well-being as including six dimensions: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance (Ryff, 1989). Autonomy is characterized by the ability to think and act independently, and it is highly valued among youth, who prioritize independence and personal choice in their lives. Environmental mastery refers to effectively adapting to one's environment. It enables youth to adjust to situational demands to maintain psychological balance. Personal growth is strongly influenced during the youth stage; the growth of both individuals and society largely depends on the potential of youth. Positive relations with others play an important role in individual development, as they help reduce stress among youth and promote the adoption of healthy coping mechanisms. Purpose in life is essential for engaging individuals in meaningful work and maintaining their motivation. Self-acceptance is also an important component of psychological well-being, as it motivates individuals to identify and accept their strengths and weaknesses.

For youths, psychological well-being is manifested in emotional stability, self-assurance, the pursuit of meaningful objectives, positive social connections, and a feeling of purpose. Souri and Hasanirad (2011) showed the strong connection between psychological well-being, resilience, and optimism. It suggests that resilient and optimistic individuals cope effectively with adversity and have positive mental health. Similarly, Long et al. (2020) conducted a study on 12,998 older adults and found that a higher level of hope is associated with better physical health, a reduced risk of disorders such as cancer, fewer sleep difficulties, healthier behaviors, and enhanced psychological well-being. It indicates that hope not only contributes to managing disorders but also acts as a preventive factor. Momeni et al. (2013) identified a substantial positive correlation among spirituality, well-being, and resilience in a study including 375 students from Razi University, Iran. Research indicates that psychological well-being in youth has strong effects on adult mental health, academic success, and social adaptation. Kalonia et al. (2023) examined the relationship among life satisfaction, resilience, and psychological well-being in a cohort of 200 university students aged 17 to 25. The study utilizing validated psychological scales identified a positive association between resilience and life satisfaction, suggesting that increased resilience levels boost well-being. The research indicated that resilience is essential for assisting students in overcoming problems like academic stress, financial hardships, and interpersonal relationships.

Hope

Hope is a strong desire that is constantly sought after, even though it's not certain that the desire will be fulfilled (Martin, 2011). One of the famous notions of hope originates from Snyder (2002) who characterizes hope as a predominantly cognitive, goal-directed thought process wherein individuals devise many 'pathways' to attain their objectives, sustain motivation to pursue these pathways, and proactively seek other routes to these goals as required. Snyder (2002) conceptualized hope as a cognitive-motivational construct consisting of three components: goals, which serve as the desired outcomes individuals aspire to attain; agency, which reflects the

motivational force and self-belief needed to pursue those outcomes; and pathways, which represent the planned strategies and alternative routes generated to achieve the identified goals. Bailey et al. (2007) found that hope is significantly associated with subjective well-being, suggesting that individuals with higher levels of hope tend to report positive emotional experiences. Similarly, Sun et al. (2023) studied the relation between hope, resilience, and mental health. The findings suggest that hope is related to better mental health and resilience. Resilience also acts as a mediator between hope and mental health. A hopeful temperament typically enhances our happiness, and a positive state of well-being often reinforces our optimism for a good future. Hope significantly influences life satisfaction, good affect, and negative affect (Muyan-Yılık & Demir, 2019). Individuals with greater hope exhibit enhanced creativity and demonstrate increased tenacity in achieving their objectives, potentially leading to elevated satisfaction through the accumulation of successful experiences (Snyder, 2000; Bailey et al., 2007).

Hope predicts enhanced life satisfaction, elevated positive affect, decreased negative affect, and hence, better subjective well-being (Snyder, 2002). A hopeful approach to problems can lead to increased resilience and mental well-being (Lee & Chen, 2020). A study by Guse and Vermaak (2011) investigated the occurrence and patterns of hope and psychosocial well-being among South African young people across different racial groupings. Socio-economic statuses were considered a moderating variable in the association between hope and psychosocial well-being. The findings showed that young people from different racial backgrounds had high levels of hope. They also had good psychosocial well-being, and race did not significantly affect their emotional well-being. A statistically substantial correlation exists between hope and psychological well-being. Velez et al. (2024) examined the relationship between dispositional hope, well-being, and mental health among 471 Portuguese citizens. The findings indicated that mental health is positively associated with both well-being and dispositional hope. Mental health was found to mediate the relationship between well-being and dispositional hope. Alam and Mohanty (2024) provided a hope-based intervention among senior secondary school students in the Bokaro district of Jharkhand, and the findings indicated that it increased their hope, self-worth, and life satisfaction. The findings collectively suggest that hope acts as an active psychological resource to promote the overall well-being of individuals.

Resilience

Resilience is the ability to deal with stress, trauma, or big problems and bounce back (Masten, 2001). Resilience is generally considered a dynamic process influenced by personal, social, and environmental factors. The American Psychological Association (2020) defines resilience as the dynamic process by which individuals adapt well to stressful situations, including trauma, danger, or significant pressures. Resilience is an essential concept to comprehend, since it enables individuals to maintain health or quickly recover from adversity, rather than only indicating well-being (Rutten et al., 2013).

Resilience models stress things that can help, such as staying positive, solving problems, controlling your emotions, getting help from others, and finding value in things. Sharma et al. (2014) found that effective resilience and stress management mitigate depression and anxiety, which leads to enhanced individual well-being. Researchers generally agree that resilience and psychological well-

being are highly connected (He et al., 2018; Rios-Risquez et al., 2018). Resilience is widely recognized as a protective factor that buffers individuals against psychological distress and fosters greater emotional stability, life satisfaction, and overall mental health (Luthar et al., 2000). Some research indicates that resilience functions as a mediating factor; a study conducted by Nath and Pradhan (2012) examined the mediating role of psychological resilience in the relationship between positive affect and psychological well-being. The results indicated that psychological resilience acts as a mediator in the relationship between psychological well-being, physical health, and positive affect.

In youth, resilience helps in the effective management of academic stress, family problems, peer pressure, and socio-cultural problems. Resilient youth show emotional strength, adaptability, and an optimistic perspective, all of which are important for maintaining mental health. Akbari and Khormaiee (2015) studied the relationship between resilience, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being among high school students. The research, including 405 students from four high schools in Shiraz, used standardized scales for emotional intelligence, resilience, and well-being. The findings demonstrated that resilience was a significant predictor of psychological well-being and served as a mediator in the interaction between emotional intelligence and mental health. The study promotes the integration of resilience training into educational programs to improve students' coping mechanisms and emotional regulation skills.

Hope, Resilience, and Psychological Well-being

Various empirical studies suggest a strong positive correlation between psychological well-being, resilience, and hope in young people (Snyder, 2002; Gallagher & Lopez, 2009). Resilience promotes emotional stability and adaptive coping; similarly, hope improves motivation and goal clarity (Masten, 2001; Snyder, 2002). Hope is also characterized as an emotional process of psychological force or buffer that enhances individuals' resilience and helps them cope with disturbances (Fredrickson et al., 2003). Moreover, resilience has been positively associated with well-being and has mediated the association between coping methods and well-being (Tomás et al., 2012).

Li and Hasson (2020) conducted a systematic review to gather data on the interactions between resilience, stress, and well-being in undergraduate nursing students from a variety of countries. The analysis suggests that the level of resilience was moderate; stress levels were elevated, and a portion of nursing students reported experiencing impaired psychological health. Stress and well-being were significantly correlated with resilience. It was found that resilience and minimal stress are more accurate indicators of well-being. A study by Shan and Xu (2025), conducted on 562 undergraduate students in mainland China, found that hope, academic thriving, and adaptive coping are associated with students' peace of mind.

Research repeatedly indicates that youth exhibiting elevated levels of hope and resilience demonstrate enhanced life satisfaction, positive affect, self-esteem, and a sense of purpose (Yıldırım & Arslan, 2020). Yan et al. (2024) conducted a systematic review on resilience, dispositional hope, and psychological well-being. The findings suggest that hope and resilience act as protective factors against stress, depression, anxiety, and academic burnout and function as strengthening factors that enhance psychological well-being. The positive associations between resilience and hope, and

their associations with quality of life, have been widely reported in previous studies (Li et al., 2016). Yıldırım (2019) found, in a study of Turkish adults, that resilience was positively correlated with life satisfaction, positive affect, affect balance, and flourishing, while negatively correlated with negative affect.

Pidgeon and Keye (2014) examined the significance of mindfulness and resilience in forecasting psychological well-being among college students. Significant positive correlations between mindfulness and resilience were identified. Resilience explained the greatest variance in the regression analysis, indicating that mindfulness and resilience predicted the variance in psychological well-being ratings. Tan et al. (2021) examined students' psychological well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic and investigated the impact of resiliency and environmental stressors related to the pandemic on psychological health. They collected data from 1,871 university students in China. The results showed that during the outbreak, resilience significantly positively influenced psychological health. Environmental stress has a moderate influence, resulting in a slight decline in psychological well-being. The magnitude of the estimations indicated that enhancing resilience can effectively reduce the adverse impacts of environmental stress on psychological well-being.

Implications and Future Directions

The continuous positive association between hope, resilience, and psychological well-being across studies has been found. The review shows that psychological well-being is directly related to hope and resilience. It highlights the importance of the development of positive assets—hope and resilience. It has major implications for mental health promotion. Psychological well-being among youth can be improved by interventions focused on enhancing hope and resilience. Mindfulness practices, strengths-based counseling, and life skills training can be helpful in this. Educational institutions and mental health organizations can significantly contribute by including positive psychology interventions into curricula and youth development initiatives. Mental health programs and policies for youth can include strategies focused on hope and resilience to promote psychological well-being. These efforts may foster healthier, more adaptable, and mentally resilient future generations. Most studies reviewed were cross-sectional. Longitudinal studies are needed to study causal relationships. Research should explore mediating and moderating variables, which can give a comprehensive understanding of their relationships. It should also study the relationship between hope, resilience, and psychological well-being in diverse cultures. Different uses of methodological approaches can give a detailed understanding of their interrelations.

Conclusion

The present review shows that hope and resilience are two important psychological resources that improve the psychological well-being of youth. Many stressors, including academic stress, social comparison, and the impact are faced by young people. They need internal psychological resources that help them deal with stress and problems. The examined literature shows that higher levels of hope and resilience are connected with greater life satisfaction, positive affect, self-esteem, academic achievement, and a stronger sense of purpose. Overall, when young people develop hope and resilience, it helps them grow into emotionally healthy, adaptable, and purpose-driven youths.

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Received March 27, 2026

Revision received April 7, 2026

Accepted April 11, 2026